

Potential of Hollow-Core Fibers to Reduce Number of in-line Amplifiers in Optical Transport Networks

Bruno Correia^{(1)*}, and João Pedro^(1,2)

⁽¹⁾*Infinera Unipessoal Lda, Rua da Garagem 1, 2790-078 Carnaxide, Portugal;*

⁽²⁾*Instituto de Telecomunicações, Instituto Superior Técnico, Avenida Rovisco Pais 1, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal*

*bruno.correia@nokia.com

Abstract—Hollow-core fibers (HCF) technologies are evolving rapidly and becoming a candidate for next generation deployable optical fibers. This type of fibers has several advantages compared with traditional ones, e.g., reduced latency, very low nonlinearities, and theoretical lower loss profile. Conversely, as they are still under development, some uncertainties are present, like their actual loss profile and costs of fabrication/deployment. Moreover, exploiting their potential for improved reach/capacity requires optical amplifiers with higher maximum total output power. Interestingly, HCF properties could be leveraged to simplify the optical network infrastructure by reducing the number of in-line amplifiers. This work assesses the potential of HCF to reduce the total number of in-line amplifiers, without compromising end-to-end performance and considering the loss coefficient uncertainty, in reference optical transport networks. Simulation results provide evidence that significant savings in in-line amplifiers are possible, while also guaranteeing high traffic load supported and reduced number of interfaces required, provided that high-power amplifiers and HCF with a loss coefficient equal or lower than traditional silica-based fibers are commercially available.

Index Terms—hollow-core fiber, network optimization, optical performance, wavelength division multiplexing

I. INTRODUCTION

In addition to the regular traffic increase in optical transport networks [1], recent and forthcoming applications, going from future 6G deployments [2] to interconnecting massive data centers dedicated to artificial-intelligence (AI) applications [3], will further stress the capacity requirements of these networks. In order to address this demand, several new technologies are undergoing development and, in some cases, nearing deployment. Firstly, new generations of coherent optical interfaces continue to increase per interface capacity and are now available in pluggable form factors. For instance, 800 Gbps interfaces are becoming commercially available [4], with multi-source agreement (MSA) projects focusing on 1.6 Tbps interfaces [5]. Secondly, there is research and development activities on ultra wide-band (UWB) technologies [6], which aim at exploiting spectral regions of the optical of the fiber beyond the C-band and which still feature relatively low attenuation. Nowadays, there are commercially available systems using extended C+L (with 4.8 THz per band) and system vendor proposals to make Super C+L solutions available [7], [8], potentially increasing the used bandwidth to 6.1 and 5.5 THz in the C- and L-band, respectively. However, it is expected that exploiting even more spectrum bands will lead to a reduction in spectral efficiency

(e.g., due to higher fiber attenuation and worse performing amplifiers) [9]. Moreover, management and control of UWB systems can be significantly more complex [10]. Finally, there are advances in space division-multiplexing (SDM), which broadly encompasses multi-mode fibers (MMF), multi-core fibers (MCF) and multiparallel fibers (MPF). These techniques allow to expand the number of orthogonal channels [11], but demand the deployment of a completely new infrastructure and specifically designed optical interfaces, in the case of both MMF and MCF.

In recent years, there has been significant progress in hollow-core fibers (HCF), to the extent that it is worth to start assessing the potential of this fiber type as an alternative to traditional standard single-mode fibers (SSMF) in future infrastructure expansion. Unlike SSMF, which uses Silica glass as transmission medium, the bulk of guided radiation in HCF propagates in gas and the interaction of this radiation with glass is limited [12]. This change in transmission medium results in several differences when compared with solid-core fiber transmission. The main advantages include: (1) as the transmission occurs through a near-vacuum medium, which has a refractive index value close to ≈ 1 , it results in an increase in transmission speed of around 50%, translating into a latency reduction of more than 30% [13]; (2) due to the intrinsic low nonlinearity characteristics, the impact of nonlinear effects on signal quality is low and stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) is negligible, which can be an advantage for UWB transmission [14]; (3) as HCF is not limited by the Rayleigh scattering [15], it presents theoretical lower losses, advantage in terms of optical performance or possible usage of longer spans, and a wider spectral low-loss region, bringing even more advantages to exploiting UWB. In addition to the stated advantages over SSMF, HCF also features an advantage over both MMF and MCF, which is the compatibility with optical interfaces originally designed for SSMF transmission. However, HCF presents some drawbacks that need to be considered. The first is the inter-modal interference (IMI), which appears due to the fundamental mode loss induced by high order modes during fiber transmission [13]. The IMI can result in a limited signal reach, albeit recent HCF designs, e.g., nested antiresonant nodeless fiber (NANF), are able to tackle this issue, minimizing this impairment to acceptable levels for signal transmission [16]. The second drawback is related to high connection losses, between HCFs and traditional fibers,

and higher splice losses, compared to silica-based fibers. Note that HCF and SSMF connections are required to exploit Erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs) for signal amplification. Although progress on reducing these extra losses has been reported in recent years [17], [18], they are still expected to be a factor impacting optical performance. Thirdly, despite several low loss records reported in the past years [19]–[21], the absence of a manufacturing process at scale, key for widespread roll out of HCF, results in a high degree of uncertainty regarding the actual loss and other properties (e.g., tolerance to bending) of these fibers, once they become commercially available. Finally, leveraging advantages (2) and (3) to increase reach and/or capacity demands being able to have higher launch power into the optical fiber, requiring the availability of EDFAs with high maximum total output power [22].

In view of the aforementioned aspects, it is paramount to gain insight on the prospects of HCFs not only in terms of latency reduction [23] and improved reach / higher fiber capacity [22], but also how this new type of fiber can be exploited to simplify the optical network infrastructure. Hence, this work evaluates the potential of HCF to reduce the number of network elements – in-line amplifiers (ILAs) – in optical transport networks. Given the uncertainty in the attenuation coefficient of future commercially available HCFs, a parametric analysis is performed over three reference transport networks. The results highlight the conditions under which significant in-line amplifier savings can be attained.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the complete methodology utilized in this work, including details of the physical layer model considered, the fibers and amplifiers characteristics, as well as the approach used to determine the potential savings in number of in-line amplifiers. Section III describes the reference topologies used in the analysis, together with the set of simulation results. Finally, Section IV presents the conclusions of this work.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Performance Modeling

In this work, we utilize the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR) [24] metric to compute the quality of transmission (QoT) of a lightpath (LP). When transmitting over regular SSMF, this metric accounts for the impact of the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) and of the nonlinear interference (NLI), generated by optical amplification and fiber transmission, respectively. In addition to these two noise sources, the IMI contribution is added when transmitting over a HCF based on the NANF design [13]. As result, the GSNR of a given optical channel can be computed by:

$$\text{GSNR} = \frac{P_{\text{ch}}}{P_{\text{ASE}} + P_{\text{NLI}} + P_{\text{IMI}}} \quad (1)$$

where P_{ch} is the evaluated channel power and P_{ASE} , P_{NLI} and P_{IMI} are the ASE, NLI and IMI power levels, respectively.

TABLE I: Fibers characterization.

	SSMF	NANF
Avr. loss [dB/km]	0.21	0.11 – 0.21
Avr. CD [$ps/(nm^2 \cdot km)$]	16.8	3.0
Avr. CD slope [$ps/(nm \cdot km)$]	0.058	0.0
Effective area [μm^2]	83	417
Nonlinear coeff. [$1/(W \cdot km)$]	1.12	$5.01e^{-4}$
Raman gain coeff. peak [$1/(W \cdot km)$]	≈ 0.4	0.0
Splice loss per 2 km [dB]	0.02	0.18

B. Fiber Characterization

To model the difference in performance between scenarios, we need to properly define the key fiber parameters, such as loss, chromatic dispersion (CD), CD slope, effective area, nonlinear coefficient and Raman gain coefficient peak. All these parameters are presented in Table I for both SSMF and NANF fiber types and in terms of average value (Avr.) when the parameter is frequency-dependent. Additionally, as the NANF technology is still evolving and there are uncertainties regarding which will be the actual loss profile for this fiber, we vary this parameter between the lowest record presented so far [21] and the same profile of SSMF (i.e., between 0.11 and 0.21 dB/km). We would also like to highlight that in this work SRS is neglected – i.e., Raman gain coefficient peak is set to zero – when modelling NANF transmission, as suggested in [14]. Moreover, it can be noticed that the last parameter presented in Table I, the splice loss per every 2 km of fiber, exhibits a large difference between both fibers, increasing from 0.02 with SSMF to 0.18 with NANF. The value used for NANF was reported in [18]. Finally, the IMI value used in this work for NANF transmission is -50.0 dB/km, a value chosen within the range (-55 to -45 dB/km) of measured values in recent experimental works [14], [20]. Note that this value is significantly above the reference value of -60.0 dB/km, which was shown to have a negligible impact on performance in [13].

C. Line System Characterization

In traditional silica-based fibers, like SSMF, the optimum launch power into the fiber (e.g., to maximize GSNR) is upper limited by the impact of nonlinear impairments. This limitation is taken into account when designing commercial EDFAs, which currently feature a maximum total output power that is typically below 27 dBm, although specialized EDFAs that can deliver up to 30 dBm are available [25]. Importantly, in view of the very low nonlinear coefficient of NANF [12], [13], a higher launch power into the fiber can be exploited to improve performance. Therefore, there is a clear incentive to deploy EDFAs featuring a higher maximum total output power in optical networks based on this type of fiber. Bearing this in mind, we carried out the analysis using both values of maximum total output power (27.0 and 30.0 dBm) and adding two more (33.0 and 36.0 dBm) to cover a wider range of values as a reasonable forecast of future amplifier generations

customized for NANF deployments. Note that these maximum total output powers are per-band, since it is still assumed that separate optical amplifiers will be used for each transmission band.

In the following, we assume a wide-band WDM transmission system comprising SuperC and SuperL bands with a spectral bandwidth of 6.1 and 5.5 THz, respectively, and a guard-band of 300 GHz between them [7]. The noise-figure of these EDFAs are assumed to be 5.5 and 6.0 dB for SuperC- and SuperL-band, respectively. When computing GSNR, it is assumed each band is filled with 120 Gbaud signals transmitted over 150 GHz frequency slots, which results in a total of 40 and 36 channels in the SuperC- and SuperL-band, respectively. The power per channel launched into each individual SSMF span is found by a search-grid method, while the power per channel for the NANF case is set depending on the maximum amplifier output power.

D. In-line Amplifier Minimization Algorithm

As referred, although NANF proprieties can be leveraged to reduce latency and increase capacity/reach, another option it to exploit the very low or even negligible impact of nonlinearities and (potentially) lower loss coefficient to reduce the number of ILAs required. Significant reductions in ILAs would lead to a sharp decrease in the total number of sites that need to be rented, powered and maintained in regional, long-haul and ultra-long-haul networks, resulting in long-term savings in operational expenditures.

In this work, it is assumed that the decrease in ILAs when using NANF spans instead of SSMF ones is conditioned on: (1) not compromising end-to-end performance, when compared to the original network topology based on SSMF; (2) using only the existing sites along each optical multiplex section (OMS) to host ILAs (i.e., amplifier site location cannot be changed). To illustrate the process of optimizing the number and location of the remaining ILAs, an example with a single OMS is presented in Fig. 1, comprising three possible configurations. The first OMS configuration is the original one, composed of five SSMF spans – ranging from 60.1 to 88.4 km – and four ILAs with a GSNR of 28.9 dB. The second OMS configuration replaces the SSMF spans by NANF spans with average loss of 0.16 dB/km, assuming ILAs capable of delivering up to 30 dBm of total output power. Under these conditions, the second ILA in the OMS can be removed (merging the spans with 60.1 and 77.4 km into a single span of 137.5 km) while keeping the OMS GSNR at a level equal or above (29.0 dB) that of the first case. In the third OMS configuration shown in Fig. 1, it is assumed that the ILAs can deliver 36 dBm. In this case, an additional ILA can be removed from the OMS, resulting in a GSNR of 30.4 dB.

The detailed procedure of how this optimization is performed is shown in Algorithm 1. Between lines 2 and 21, the algorithm iterates over all OMSs of the network topology. The number of ILAs and the GSNR of the original OMSs is used as reference. In line 5, C receives all possible combinations, removing at least one ILA, of the evaluated OMS to be tested

Fig. 1: Illustration of ILA removal from an OMS by replacing SSMF with NANF.

Algorithm 1 Network design update with new OMS configuration with NANF.

Input: OMS_{SSMF} : list of topology OMSs using SSMF;
 P_{SSMF} : SSMF parameters;
 P_{NANF} : NANF parameters;
 P_{amp} : Amplifier parameters;

Output: OMS_{NANF} : list of topology OMSs using NANF;

- 1: $\text{OMS}_{\text{NANF}} \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 2: **for all** oms **in** OMS_{SSMF} **do**
- 3: $\text{ILA}_{\text{best}} \leftarrow$ number of ILAs of oms;
- 4: $\text{GSNR}_{\text{best}} \leftarrow \text{GSNR}(\text{oms}, P_{\text{SSMF}})$;
- 5: $C \leftarrow$ List of possible OMSs configurations, removing at least one ILA;
- 6: $c_{\text{best}} \leftarrow \emptyset$;
- 7: **for all** c **in** C **do**
- 8: $\text{ILA}_{\text{NANF}} \leftarrow$ number of ILAs of c ;
- 9: $\text{GSNR}_{\text{NANF}} \leftarrow \text{GSNR}(\text{oms}, P_{\text{NANF}}, P_{\text{amp}})$
- 10: **if** $\text{GSNR}_{\text{NANF}} \geq \text{GSNR}_{\text{best}}$ **and** $\text{ILA}_{\text{NANF}} < \text{ILA}_{\text{best}}$ **then**
- 11: $\text{ILA}_{\text{best}} \leftarrow \text{ILA}_{\text{NANF}}$;
- 12: $\text{GSNR}_{\text{best}} \leftarrow \text{GSNR}_{\text{NANF}}$;
- 13: $c_{\text{best}} \leftarrow c$;
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **end for**
- 16: **if** $c_{\text{best}} \neq \emptyset$ **then**
- 17: $\text{OMS}_{\text{NANF}} \leftarrow \text{OMS}_{\text{NANF}} \cup c_{\text{best}}$
- 18: **else**
- 19: $\text{OMS}_{\text{NANF}} \leftarrow \text{OMS}_{\text{NANF}} \cup \text{oms}$
- 20: **end if**
- 21: **end for**

with NANF. For each of these combinations (between lines 7 and 15), the algorithm evaluates (line 10) which one presents the highest amount of ILAs removed while maintaining a GSNR equal or higher than the best GSNR found up to that point. After the algorithm iterates over all possible OMS combinations, the new set of OMSs with NANF (OMS_{NANF}) is updated with the best combination or, if no combination meets the criteria of line 10, with the same OMS structure.

Fig. 2: Reference optical network topologies of (a) TEF, (b) TIM National, and (c) CORONET.

TABLE II: Network topologies characteristics.

	TEF	TIM	CORONET
#ROADMs	30	44	75
#OMSs	112	142	198
#Spans	244	400	1072
Avr. OMS span count	2.18	2.82	5.41
Avr. OMS length	148.44	184.13	396.62
Max. span length	101.7	100.0	80.0
Avr. span length	67.5	58.6	70.7

It is worth mentioning that cost of HCF deployment is not considered in this work, but could be added in future works to show the tradeoff between costs of deployment and versus savings from ILAs reduction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Simulation Setup

In order to comprehensively assess the potential of deploying NANF spans to reduce the number of ILAs, three different reference network topologies were considered. Fig. 2(a) shows the Telefónica (TEF) network topology, covering Spain and composed of 30 ROADMs nodes and 112 OMSs, Fig. 2(b) presents the Telecom Italia (TIM) network topology, covering Italy with 44 ROADMs nodes and 142 OMSs, and finally, Fig. 2(c) illustrates the CORONET topology, covering continental USA with 75 ROADMs nodes and 198 OMSs. The key parameters describing these reference network topologies are presented in Table II. The length of the shortest path between the nodes farthest apart in these topologies is 944, 2297, and 6479 km for TEF, TIM, and CORONET, respectively. Hence, the first two network topologies can be broadly classified as regional / long-haul, whereas the third can be classified as ultra-long-haul.

The GSNR estimation for a given path is done based on the disaggregated approach, where the total GSNR is composed by the contributions of each span GSNR [26]. Moreover, we set ROADMs losses to 20 dB and transmitter optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) to 37 dB/0.1nm. In order to gain insight into the network-wide impact of the different OMS configurations that result from realizing ILA savings, a full network design exercise is also reported for a sub-set of the configurations. Hence, for each network, 10 traffic matrices were randomly generated for different values of offered traffic load and following a uniform distribution between the node pairs. The client signals are assumed to be 800 GbE, which are preferably allocated to one 150 GHz channel using 16QAM modulation format, which has a required OSNR (ROSNR) of 27 dB/0.1nm. Alternatively, longer paths can be realized via two channels (300 GHz) with QPSK modulation format, which has a ROSNR of 20 dB/0.1nm. These channel formats are based on the OpenROADM MSA [27]. Moreover, a 3 dB of margin is added when computing every path GSNR in order to account for component aging and impairments not explicitly modelled (e.g., filtering, polarization dependent losses).

B. Simulation Results

The algorithm described in sub-section II-D was applied to the network topologies introduced in sub-section III-A. Fig. 3 presents the share of network ILAs that can be removed without compromising end-to-end performance as a function of the NANF average loss for the three topologies illustrated in Fig. 2. One curve is shown for each value considered for the amplifiers' maximum total output power.

Fig. 3(a) shows the results for the TEF topology. For the lowest NANF loss value considered (0.11 dBm), the share of ILAs removed ranges from 29% with amplifiers similar to the ones deployed today (27 dBm maximum output power) to more than 72%, when increasing the maximum output power to 30 dBm, and up to around 83% when further increasing this value to 33 or 36 dBm amplifiers. As the NANF loss coefficient increases, the percentage of removed ILAs decreases in almost all cases except for the case with the 36 dBm amplifier, which for up to 0.14 dB/km remain almost constant and above 80%. This can be explained by the fact that with high output power, even higher losses can be tolerated to achieve the same OMS performance of SSMF. Conversely, with 27 dBm amplifiers, no significantly ILA savings are possible for a NANF loss coefficient higher than 0.15 dBm. Note that, although this loss coefficient is still lower than the SSMF one, the higher splice losses of NANF result in comparable total link losses. This circumstance, coupled with the relatively limited per channel launch power, prevents achieving ILA savings in this scenario. If the maximum amplifier output power increases, more than 10% ILA savings can already be achieved for 0.17, 0.19, and 0.21 dBm/km when using amplifiers that can deliver 30, 33 and 36 dBm, respectively.

The plot in Fig. 3(b) shows the ILA savings obtained for the TIM reference topology. ILA savings of up to 41%, 56%, 60%,

Fig. 3: In-line amplifier savings as a function of the NANF loss coefficient in (a) TEF, (b) TIM, and (c) CORONET.

and 67% are possible when using amplifiers with a maximum output power of 27, 30, 33, and 36 dBm, respectively. For higher NANF average losses, e.g. 0.16 dB/km, the percentage of ILA savings is higher than 10% for amplifier output powers higher or equal than 30 dBm, while for 0.21 dB/km, this level of savings is only observed for a maximum output power of 36 dBm. When comparing the ILA savings obtained in this topology against those reported in the TEF topology, two main observations can be made. On one hand, the maximum attainable ILA savings (i.e., for a maximum output power of 36 dBm and low fiber losses) are smaller in the TIM topology than that in the TEF topology, which is a consequence of the former having longer OMSs (see Table II). On the other hand, the TIM topology has a shorter average span length than that of TEF, which allows to realize comparable ILA savings when using more limited launch powers (i.e., for amplifiers with a maximum output power of 27 dBm).

Finally, Fig. 3(c) presents the results for the CORONET reference topology. The ILA savings in this ultra-long-haul topology are comparatively smaller than those obtained with TEF and TIM, since it has longer average lengths for both

TABLE III: Network simulation results for BP = 1%.

Topology	Fiber (Pow.)	Traff. [Tbps]	# Interf.	# ILAs
TEF	SSMF	382	2.5	264
	NANF (30)	416	1.7	220
	NANF (36)	396	1.9	108
TIM	SSMF	119	2.7	516
	NANF (30)	172	2.6	400
	NANF (36)	202	2.5	248
CORONET	SSMF	115	4.3	1748
	NANF (30)	124	3.7	1512
	NANF (36)	115	3.8	1096

OMSs and fiber spans. Still, it is feasible to achieve savings close to 60% for amplifiers with 33 and 36 dBm, 46% with 30 dBm and 25% with 27 dBm. Moreover, similar to TEF topology, the ILA savings with 36 dBm amplifiers present a variation of less than 5% for NANF losses higher or equal than 0.19 dB/km. Ultimately, for NANF losses higher or equal than 0.19 dB/km, the ILA savings of all four amplifier types present close values, varying between 5% and 15% for lowest and highest amplifier powers, respectively.

Table III presents the network simulation results assuming as a target that the network should be loaded up to a blocking probability (BP) of 1%. Three OMS configurations are considered for each network topology – original with SSMF and modified with NANF spans with 0.14 dB/km and EDFAs having a maximum total output power of 30 and 36 dBm. The results reported include the total offered traffic load for the target BP, the average number of utilized optical interface pairs to support this traffic load per connection established, and the total number of ILAs in the network. Both the offered traffic load and number of interfaces are the average value of the 10 independent simulation runs. The results show that the ILA savings from deploying NANF generally result in a similar offered traffic load for the target BP. In some cases this value can actually be improved (e.g., in TIM). The reason for the reported increase is due to the better path GSNR values that can be obtained in the OMS configurations based on NANF. This occurs because of the criteria used to save ILAs, since it must be ensured that the per OMS GSNR is always kept equal or above that of the SSMF case. Therefore, in many OMSs the GSNR will be at least slightly higher than that in the original topology and, consequently, for some paths the accumulated improvement may allow to use 16QAM instead of QPSK, improving spectral efficiency and enabling to carry more traffic load. It is also worth mentioning that the number of utilized optical interfaces is always smaller in the NANF-based OMS configurations than in the original ones. These results validate the ILA savings approach from the perspective of ensuring both equal or higher traffic load and equal or smaller optical interface requirements.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper assessed the potential of HCF to reduce the number of in-line amplifiers in optical transport networks

while guaranteeing equal or better performance than traditional SSMF. The analysis considered different system parameters, i.e., HCF loss profile and total amplifier output power, and three reference networks. The simulation results suggest that savings in in-line amplifiers, which also decrease the number of physical sites that need to be powered and maintained, tend to increase in network topologies with shorter span lengths and when using amplifiers with higher maximum total output power. Although amplifier savings are already possible if the deployed HCF has a loss coefficient similar to SSMF, high savings, even exceeding 80% in one of the reference networks, would be viable if HCF with a loss coefficient close to the one reported in recent records becomes commercially available.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from EU Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under GA 101092766 (ALLEGRO), FCT/MECI through national funds and when applicable co-funded EU funds under UID/50008: Instituto de Telecomunicações.

REFERENCES

- [1] CISCO, "Cisco Annual Internet Report (2018–2023)," <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/collateral/executive-perspectives/annual-internet-report/white-paper-c11-741490.html>, 2020. [Online; accessed 28-January-2025].
- [2] C.-X. Wang, X. You, X. Gao, X. Zhu, Z. Li, C. Zhang, H. Wang, Y. Huang, Y. Chen, H. Haas, J. S. Thompson, E. G. Larsson, M. D. Renzo, W. Tong, P. Zhu, X. Shen, H. V. Poor, and L. Hanzo, "On the road to 6g: Visions, requirements, key technologies, and testbeds," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 25, pp. 905–974, 2023.
- [3] P. A. Baziana, "Optical data center networking: A comprehensive review on traffic, switching, bandwidth allocation, and challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 186413–186444, 2024.
- [4] Infinera, "ICE-X 800G ZR+ QSFP-DD800 and OSFP," <https://www.infinera.com/products/ice-x-800g-zr-plus/>, 2024. [Online; accessed 28-January-2025].
- [5] L. Wilkinson. <https://www.oiforum.com/oif-launches-1600zr-coherent-optical-retimed-tx-linear-rx-optical-energy-efficient-interfaces-projects-and-common-management-interface-specification-white-paper-at-q1-2024-technical-and-mae-meeting/>, 2024. [Online; accessed 28-January-2025].
- [6] T. Hoshida, V. Curri, L. Galdino, D. T. Neilson, W. Forsyiaik, J. K. Fischer, T. Kato, and P. Poggiolini, "Ultrawideband systems and networks: Beyond C + L-band," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, pp. 1–17, 2022.
- [7] J. Pedro and A. Souza, "Impact of channel provisioning strategies in the transient resiliency of SuperC+L-band networks," in *2024 14th International Workshop on Resilient Networks Design and Modeling (RNDM)*, pp. 1–7, IEEE, 11 2024.
- [8] Infinera, "Addressing the Shannon Dilemma with Super C and Super L," <https://www.infinera.com/white-paper/addressing-the-shannon-dilemma-with-superc-and-superl/>, 2024. [Online; accessed 29-January-2025].
- [9] L. Rapp and M. Eiselt, "Optical amplifiers for multi-band optical transmission systems," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 40, pp. 1579–1589, 3 2022.
- [10] B. Correia, R. Sadeghi, E. Virgillito, A. Napoli, N. Costa, J. Pedro, and V. Curri, "Power control strategies and network performance assessment for C+L+S multiband optical transport," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 13, p. 147, 7 2021.
- [11] W. Klaus, B. J. Puttnam, R. S. Luís, J. Sakaguchi, J.-M. D. Mendinueta, Y. Awaji, and N. Wada, "Advanced space division multiplexing technologies for optical networks," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 9, p. C1, 4 2017.
- [12] K. Borzycki and T. Osuch, "Hollow-core optical fibers for telecommunications and data transmission," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, p. 10699, 9 2023.
- [13] P. Poggiolini and F. Poletti, "Opportunities and challenges for long-distance transmission in hollow-core fibres," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 40, pp. 1605–1616, 3 2022.
- [14] A. Nespola, S. Straullu, T. D. Bradley, K. Harrington, H. Sakr, G. T. Jasion, E. N. Fokoua, Y. Jung, Y. Chen, J. R. Hayes, F. Forghieri, D. J. Richardson, F. Poletti, G. Bosco, and P. Poggiolini, "Transmission of 61 C-band channels over record distance of hollow-core-fiber with L-band interferers," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 39, pp. 813–820, 2 2021.
- [15] H. Sakr, Y. Chen, G. T. Jasion, T. D. Bradley, J. R. Hayes, H. C. H. Mulvad, I. A. Davidson, E. N. Fokoua, and F. Poletti, "Hollow core optical fibres with comparable attenuation to silica fibres between 600 and 1100nm," *Nature Communications*, vol. 11, p. 6030, 11 2020.
- [16] A. Nespola, S. R. Sandoghchi, L. Hooper, M. Alonso, T. D. Bradley, H. Sakr, G. T. Jasion, E. N. Fokoua, S. Straullu, F. Garrisi, G. Bosco, A. Carena, A. M. R. Busin, Y. Chen, J. R. Hayes, F. Forghieri, D. J. Richardson, F. Poletti, and P. Poggiolini, "Ultra-long-haul WDM transmission in a reduced inter-modal interference NANF hollow-core fiber," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2021*, p. F3B.5, Optica Publishing Group, 2021.
- [17] D. Suslov, M. Komanec, E. R. N. Fokoua, D. Dousek, A. Zhong, S. Zvánovec, T. D. Bradley, F. Poletti, D. J. Richardson, and R. Slavík, "Low loss and high performance interconnection between standard single-mode fiber and antiresonant hollow-core fiber," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 11, p. 8799, 4 2021.
- [18] A. Zhong, E. N. Fokoua, M. Ding, D. Dousek, D. Suslov, S. Zvánovec, F. Poletti, R. Slavík, and M. Komanec, "Connecting hollow-core and standard single-mode fibers with perfect mode-field size adaptation," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 42, pp. 2124–2130, 3 2024.
- [19] G. T. Jasion, T. D. Bradley, K. Harrington, H. Sakr, Y. Chen, E. N. Fokoua, I. A. Davidson, A. Taranta, J. R. Hayes, D. J. Richardson, and F. Poletti, "Hollow core NANF with 0.28 dB/km attenuation in the C and L bands," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference Postdeadline Papers 2020*, p. Th4B.4, Optica Publishing Group, 2020.
- [20] G. T. Jasion, H. Sakr, J. R. Hayes, S. R. Sandoghchi, L. Hooper, E. N. Fokoua, A. Saljoghei, H. C. Mulvad, M. Alonso, A. Taranta, T. D. Bradley, I. A. Davidson, Y. Chen, D. J. Richardson, and F. Poletti, "0.174 dB/km hollow core double nested antiresonant nodeless fiber (DNANF)," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2022*, p. Th4C.7, Optica Publishing Group, 2022.
- [21] Y. Chen, M. Petrovich, E. N. Fokoua, A. Adamu, M. Hassan, H. Sakr, R. Slavík, S. B. Gorajooobi, M. Alonso, R. F. Ando, A. Papadimopoulos, T. Varghese, D. Wu, M. F. Ando, K. Wisniowski, S. Sandoghchi, G. Jasion, D. Richardson, and F. Poletti, "Hollow core DNANF optical fiber with 0.11 dB/km loss," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2024*, p. Th4A.8, Optica Publishing Group, 2024.
- [22] B. Correia, J. Pedro, and N. Costa, "Hollow-core fiber specifications for competitive deployment in regio/long-haul optical networks," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2025*, Optica Publishing Group, 2025.
- [23] G. Martinez, J. Conde, P. Reviriego, J. A. Hernandez, and P. Reinheimer, "Opportunities of hollow-core fibers at reducing internet latency," in *Proceedings - 2023 IEEE Future Networks World Forum: Future Networks: Imagining the Network of the Future, FNWF 2023*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2023.
- [24] A. Ferrari, M. Filer, K. Balasubramanian, Y. Yin, E. L. Rouzic, J. Kundrát, G. Grammel, G. Galimberti, and V. Curri, "GNPy: an open source application for physical layer aware open optical networks," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 12, p. C31, 6 2020.
- [25] M. C. Inc. https://mpbcommunications.com/en/site/products/network_ready_telecom_solutions/2RU-Series/boosters/index.html. Accessed: 2024-10-21.
- [26] V. Curri, "Software-defined wdm optical transport in disaggregated open optical networks," in *22nd International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON)*, pp. 1–4, IEEE, 7 2020.
- [27] OpenROADM, "OpenROADM specifications v7.0," <https://view.officeapps.live.com/ov/view.aspx?src=https> [Online; accessed 07-February-2025].